

NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE CHANGES IN ADOLESCENT
BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: In this article, the peculiarities of studying the manifestation of behavioral deviations in adolescents and some general aspects related to behavioral deviations in adolescence are studied from the point of view of social psychology, the interaction of adolescents in the development of society. and the scientific studies that can show the necessity of the problem of their behavior in conflict situations and justify its "methodological roots" are highlighted.

Keywords: behavior, adolescence, deviance, demonstrativeness, verbal aggressiveness, aggressiveness.

Beginning of mankind, the development of children has been regarded as an important problem in society. Because, as long as the society exists, all qualities and ideological views of a person are absorbed into his character, mind, and thinking. The purpose, content and requirements of education continue to change with the change of society, the passage of time and the development of time.

Adolescence is the most complex and at the same time important stage of development. Early adolescence includes 11-13 years old, senior adolescence - 14-15 years old. Adolescence is characterized by intensity and unevenness in the development of the body, during which intensive development of the body and hardening of bones occur. There is also an imbalance in the activity of the heart and blood vessels, which also causes the child's behavior to be variable, dynamic, and sometimes uncomfortable and uncomfortable. Of course, these have an effect on the nervous system, and the child can get angry quickly or become depressed and unable to get out of depression for a long time.

Demonstration, scientists have unanimously concluded, is one of the characteristic features of adolescent behavior. According to AE Lichko, the demonstrative reaction is "the most common affective reaction in adolescent behavior." Educators often face the problem of demonstrativeness in the behavior of adolescents. A teenager often attracts attention through lies, stupidity, and rudeness. Usually, such teenagers, selfish (egoist), do not want to correct the shortcomings of their behavior. These actions are performed not in a defensive way, but in order to win over others, to assert oneself, to attract the attention of others. The word "demonstration" comes from the Latin word "demonstration". This category is used to refer to various forms of behavior aimed at attracting the attention of others. In

addition, the ability to attract attention is a necessary feature for people in professions such as actors, politicians, athletes. The desire to stand out from others is carried out in several directions, depending on the situation, it switches from one style to another, or if the result of the style at the same time is satisfactory, the teenager may not change the style. The first method is to arouse respect and admiration and sympathy for one's own person. This method works well at school and at home. In this case, the teenager tries to distinguish himself by his success in studies, sports or participation in some club. Often, a teenager explains his failures in education with external factors. In addition, actions aimed at gaining the compassion and sympathy of those around. Various tricks are chosen for this. From telling them stories about their bad luck, getting hysterical, fainting, and even getting sick. The third method is to attract the attention of others in a negative way. In the behavior of a teenager, boldness, clowning, rudeness, deliberate violation of discipline, going against the opinion of the majority and other deviations in behavior. These include demonstrative escape and demonstrative suicide. Many psychologists associate the concept of crisis development with "character accentuation". Acknowledgment of the accentuation of the character and personal individual characteristics of the teenager allows the pedagogue to foresee the actions of the teenager. [2] According to G.Parens, aggressiveness is self-defense and protection of one's right. AA Rean and SL Solovyova also put forward the same idea. Aggression can cause the manifestation of unpleasant traits in a person's character. Bullying in the fearless form, not being able to defend one's rights in the form of fear. Also, aggression varies with other types of delinquent and criminal behavior. Changes in the forms of aggressiveness are characteristic for teenagers. LMSemenyuk (1996) conducted a study on the topic of different manifestations of aggression at different stages of adolescence. According to him, 10-11 year olds show more physical aggression. In them, relative aggression is less noticeable than all types of aggression. Adolescents aged 12-13 show more negativity, followed by physical and verbal aggression. In adolescents aged 14-15, verbal aggressiveness reaches the first level. Physical and relational types of aggression, as well as the level of negativity, increase significantly. There are also gender differences in the manifestation of aggressive reactions. The method of physical aggression is more prominent in boys. In girls, verbal aggression, indirect methods of aggression, as well as the level of negativity increase. [3]Adolescence includes age-related indicators of high and low levels of aggressive behavior that are equally relevant for boys and girls. [4] According to Semenyuk's research, 10- Physical aggression is at a high rate in 11-year-old teenagers, and verbal aggression is at the first level in 14-15-year-old teenagers. However, this is not an age-related decline in the

manifestation of physical aggression. The maximum indicators of manifestation of all forms of aggression (physical and verbal aggression) are clearly visible at the age of 14-15 years. But the growth dynamics of physical and verbal aggression are not the same as a person grows up. The manifestation of physical aggression, although increasing, is not significant. The rate of increase in the manifestation of verbal aggression in Ammon is quite fast. It can be noted that at a young age, for example, 10-11 years, the difference between different forms of aggression is significant it's not .

That is, although they are expressed differently, the differences in the frequency of their occurrence are not noticeable. Among adolescents aged 14-15 years, the frequency of occurrence of aggression is more clear and there are significant differences. The structure of the manifestation of various forms of aggression depends on age and gender characteristics at the same time. Physical aggression predominates in boys during early adolescence . In girls, physical aggression is expressed a little, but girls prefer the verbal, verbal method of aggression. Now, at the age of 12-13 , the form of aggression in both boys and girls is negativity.

Not to mention the negativity in Bass and Darkie's concept of aggression the concept of opposition is against the established laws and regulations, which can be manifested in the form of passive resistance against the existing rules, norms and customs, and in the form of active struggle. At the age of 12-13, secondary aggression is physical in boys, and verbal in girls. In adolescents aged 14-15 years, negativism and verbal aggression are dominant in boys, while in girls the form of verbal aggression is dominant. The form of physical aggression is not dominant among adolescents of this age, even in boys . It is clear that regardless of age, all forms of aggressive behavior are more common in boys than in girls .

And urgent the topic of adolescence is, and every member of society should pay attention to the psychological characteristics and changes of this age period. it is appropriate to mention that it will not happen. In the family, parents and relatives are responsible for the upbringing of the teenager, and in educational institutions, every pedagogue is responsible. In the family, we would like parents to pay attention to the following recommendations: - to be more attentive to their teenage children - to devote as much time as possible to the child - to monitor the correct distribution of free time - to be positive about their interests we would like to point out that they should pay attention to recommendations such as establishing a friendly dialogue - monitoring the establishment of a culture of correct treatment of family members . It is important for pedagogues in educational institutions to pay attention to the following when teaching teenagers: - the activity of the teenager in the lesson - his

attitude towards the school team - the establishment of consensus with peers - the interest and interest of students in the educational process It would be appropriate to pay attention to their needs - to create conditions for their independent thinking and activities in the field of their interest. We believe that these recommendations will ensure a smooth transition for teenagers.

References

1. Darovskix O.N., Nikitina E.L. Ko'rgazmali xulq-atvorga ega o'smirlarning shaxsiy xususiyatlari //Ilmiy va "Konsepsiya" uslubiy elektron jurnali. 2016. V. 28. S. 121–123.
2. Ikromova, S. (2023). INTERPRETATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY FACTOR IN RELATION TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 390-394.
3. Ikromova, S. (2023). CONCEPT OF IDEOLOGY AND FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY IN YOUTH STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(6), 1223-1226.
4. Ikromova, S. (2023). FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN TEENAGERS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1009-1014.
5. Ikromova, S. A. (2022). MILLIY VA DINIY QADRIYATLARNING INSON TARBIYASIDAGI O'RNI. *Экономика и социум*, (12-2 (103)), 675-678.
6. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). SHAXS OG 'ISHGAN XULQINING KO 'RINISHLARI VA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARNING KO 'RINISHLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 528-532.
7. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). YOSHLARDA DESTRUKTIV G'OYALARGA QARSHI IMMUNITET HOSIL QILISH OMILLARI.
8. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). TALABA YOSHLARDA MAFKURA TUSHUNCHASI VA MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITETNI SHAKLLANTIRISH.
9. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). O'SMIRLARDA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH.
10. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH IJTIMOIIY MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Barqaror Taraqqiyot va Rivojlanish Tamoyillari*, 1(6), 26-29.
11. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). MILLIY HARAKATLI O'YINLARNING BOLALAR TARBIYASIDAGI IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.
12. Sitara Akbarovna Ikromova. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 50–54.
13. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Study of the Formation of Ideological Immunity By Foreign and Russian Researchers. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 235-239.
14. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Adolescence during Destructive Behavior Appearances the Problem Learning Condition. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 105-109.
15. Ikromova Sitara Akbarovna. (2023). NEUROPHYSIOLOGY BASIS OF HORMONES. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 68–77.
16. Ikromova Sitara Akbarovna. (2023). RESEARCH METHODS OF YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

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17. Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information in Adolescents. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 119–122.
18. Ikromova, S. A. FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN ADOLESCENTS.
19. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PYTHON (PYTORCH). *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research* , 1(3), 123-126.
20. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ADVANTAGES OF DJANGO FEMWORKER. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
21. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYA YO ‘NALISHIDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN TALABALARGA SPSS YORDAMIDA MATEMATIK USULLARNI O‘RGATISHNING METODIK USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 323-326.
22. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PYTHON INSTRUMENTLARI BILAN KATTA MA'LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 320-322.
23. Jalolov, T. S., & Usmonov, A. U. (2021). “AQLLI ISSIQXONA” BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA TADQIQ QILISH. *Экономика и социум*, (9 (88)), 74-77.
24. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023). Capabilities of SPSS Software in High Volume Data Processing Testing. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 82-86.
25. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023, November). IDENTIFYING THE POSITIVE EFFECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL WORK FACTORS BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS AND DEPARTMENTS THROUGH SPSS SOFTWARE. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 18, pp. 150-153).
26. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). TEACHING THE BASICS OF PYTHON PROGRAMMING. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11).
27. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). Solving Complex Problems in Python. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 481-484.
28. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DATA PROCESSING USING THE SPSS PROGRAM. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 2(23), 220-223.
29. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). SPSS YOKI IJTIMOIY FANLAR UCHUN STATISTIK PAKET BILAN PSIXOLOGIK MA'LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 207–215.
30. Кутбединов, А. (1985). Разработка и применение ядерно-физических методов анализа подземных вод для выявления предвестников землетрясений.
31. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2021). ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ КЛАССНЫХ УРОКОВ. *Вестник науки и образования*, (15-3 (118)), 40-42.
32. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДИДАКТИЧЕСКОГО ПРОГРАММНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ МАТЕМАТИКЕ. In *НОВЫЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ* (pp. 10-12).
33. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫМ НАУКАМ. *Universum: технические науки*, (4-1 (109)), 41-43.
34. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). ВАЖНОСТЬ МАТЕМАТИКИ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК ДЛЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ: Сайфуллаева Нозима Баходировна, преподаватель кафедры “Теория начального образования”, Бухарский государственный университет. Город Бухара. Республика Узбекистан.

Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (1), 305-307.

35. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). Методы Организации Уроков Математики В Начальных Классах С Использованием Цифровых Технологий. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 35, 388-390.

36. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). РОЛЬ МАТЕМАТИКИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 1(1), 292-292.

37. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2019). Роль дидактических игр в умственном развитии учащихся в математике начального класса. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY* (pp. 102-106).

38. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Марданова, Ф. Я. (2021). НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ ПО ВЫСШЕЙ МАТЕМАТИКЕ. *Проблемы науки*, 84.

39. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2020). Важные особенности дидактических игр в процессе обучения математике в начальных школах. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ* (pp. 60-62).

40. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Мурадова, Я. М. (2020). Пути эффективного использования методов обучения математике в начальных классах. In *EUROPEAN RESEARCH* (pp. 121-123).

41. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2022). Методы определения потребностей обучающихся в процессе использования облачных технологий в образовании. *Universum: технические науки*, (2-1 (95)), 57-59.

42. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN ADOLESCENTS. *Innovation in Science, Education and Technology*